

From Mapping to Composition

Technical Workflow and Sound Design in Resonances of Stones

These activities are part of the CAPHE project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe strategic innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101086391. The perspectives and opinions expressed herein belong to their authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the funding institution is responsible for them.

Selection of music for the Bazeos Tower rooms

Agata Szlązak

Recordings made in Bazeos Tower on August 28, 2024

- Greek Orthodox chant “Kyrie Eleison”, performed by vocalist Silvia Rio
- Dimitris Papadimitriou: “Saffo”, performed by vocalist Silvia Rio and guitarist Ella Nagy
- Kassia: “The Five-stringed Lute and Fivefold Lamp”, performed by Ella Nagy on the lute

Spatial Assignment of Musical Works

Musical Work	Place	Listening effect
Kyrie eleison	The Chapel	Solo/Tutti
The Five-stringed Lute	The Small Room	Intimacy of small space acoustic
Saffo	The Pink Room	The source of the sound moving around the listener
CO ₂	The Terrace	Sculpture creation sounds

Music for The Chapel

Composition by Gianluca Aresu and Agata Szlązak

Inspiration and starting point

Byzantine chant **Kyrie eleison** from the 9th–10th century AD

Greek: **Lord have mercy on us!**

- Answer of the congregation to the prayers of the priest (Orthodox)
- Penitential responsorial prayer between the priest and the congregation (Catholic)

3-part structure ABA

The final composition

Exposition: vocal theme, repetitions, choral responses.

Central section: modal development, ancient Greek instruments, african drum instruments + electronic textures, drone as a sound continuum.

Final part: flutes, natural environment sounds, evoking African atmospheres, dilated textures and evolving timbres.

Sound sources: recorded voice and instruments, synthesized sounds and natural external soundscape

Music for The Pink Room

Composition by Gianluca Aresu

Inspiration and starting point

Song **Sapho** for voice and guitar by Dimitris Papadimitriou

Mythological motifs: **Hermes**, **Lotos**, the river of **Archiront**

Life - death, materialism - spirituality, passage to the world of the dead

ABCBA' structure

The final composition

Opening: dialogue voice - guitar, voice moving around the listener, guitar stable.

Experimental and material part: broken voice, sound of stones and masses, tactile and immersive perception.

Central part: Greek instruments, African percussion, new harmonies, reworking the main theme.

Final part: return to the original sound objects

Music for The Small Room

Composition by Roberto Cipollina

Origins of the Piece

- Original inspiration: The Five-stringed Lute and the Fivefold Lamp – hymn by Kassia, a 9th century Byzantine-Greek composer, hymnographer and poet
- Kassia is the only female author of many hymns still used in the Byzantine liturgy today

The Five-stringed Lute and the Fivefold Lamp

- The hymn is intended to be performed at matins – one of two hymns in honor of Orthodox martyrs, commemorated on December 13 (of the Julian calendar) in the Orthodox Liturgy.
- Based on five figures of martyrs from aristocratic families from Cappadocia who were executed at the end of the third century
- Number of martyrs signified by the title (five-stringed lute, fivefold lamp) as well as the use of the DO-SOL interval which is a fifth.
- Entymology of each name also used to describe the virtues of each martyr

The Five-stringed Lute and the Fivefold Lamp

**Τῆ Π' Εὐστρατίου, Αὐξεντίου, Εὐγενίου,
Μαρδάριον καὶ Ορεστες
(εἰς τὸν ὄρθρον)**

1. Τὴν πεντάχορδον λύραν,
καὶ πεντάφωτον λυχνίαν,
τῆς τοῦ Θεοῦ Ἐκκλησίας
τοῦς θεοφόρους μάρτυρας
5 φερωνύμως τιμῶμεν
καὶ εὐσεβῶς ἐγκωμιάσωμεν.
Χαίροις, ὁ καλῶς ὑπὸ Θεοῦ στρατευθεὶς
ἐν τῇ ἐπουρανίῳ στρατιᾷ,
καὶ τῷ στρατολογήσαντι ἀρέσας,
10 ὁ ἐν ῥήτορι ῥήτορ,
Εὐστράτις θεόσοφε.
Χαίροις, ὁ τὸ τάλαντον τὸ ἐκ Θεοῦ σοι πιστευθέν
ἐπαυξήσας εἰς πλῆθος,
Αὐξέντιε μακάριε.
15 Χαίροις, ὁ τερπνότατος ὄρηξ
τῆς θεϊκῆς εὐγενείας,
Εὐγένιε θεόφρον.
Χαίροις, ὁ ὡραῖος τῇ μορφῇ,
τῇ δὲ γνώμῃ ὑπερλαμπρὸς
20 καὶ ἀμφοτεροδέξιος,
ὁ ἐν τοῖς θείοις ὄρεσιν ἐνδιατώμενος ὄλως,
πανόλβιε Ὀρέστα.
Χαίροις, ὁ στίλβων καὶ διαγῆς μαργαρίτης,
ὁ τὰς βασάνους τὰς πικρὰς
25 χαρμονικῶς ὑπομείνας,
Μαρδάριε ἀήττητε.
Χαίροις, ὁ ἰσάριθους χορὸς τῶν φρονίμων
παρθένων.
Οὗς καθικετεύομεν
πάσης ὀργῆς καὶ θλίψεως λυτρώσασθαι
30 καὶ τῆς ἀφράστοθ αὐτῶν δόξης
συμμετόχους ποιῆσαι
τοῦς τὴν ἐτήσιον ἡμῶν
μνήμη γεραιόνας.

**Saints Eustratius, Auxentios, Eugenios, Mardarios and
Orestes
(at the Orthros)**

The five-stringed lute,
and five-fold lamp,
of God's Church,
the divinely inspired martyrs
so suitably named, let us honor
and reverently praise.
Hail, you who nobly served under God
in the heavenly expedition
and were pleasing to the Leader,
orator among orators,
Eustratius, wise in the things of God.
Hail, you who increased in quantity
the talent entrusted to you from God
blessed Auxentius
Hail, you who are the most pleasing descendent
of divine nobility,
godly-minded Eugenios.
Hail, you who are fair in form,
exceedingly distinguished in judgment
and always ready,
who lives forever on the mountains of God,
truly blessed Orestes
Hail, shining and radiant pearl,
who endured the bitter tortures
quietly,
unconquered Mardarius.
Hail, evenly-balanced chorus of wise virgins.
Let us entreat them
to deliver from all wrath and oppression
and make partakers
of their ineffable glory
those who celebrate
your yearly feast.

Compositional Process

- The piece is divided into six sections with the immersive experience unfolding out of time
- Voices guide the listening experience with main voice at the center of the space and the rest of the voices are dispersed in the surrounding space
- Added to the voices are moving whispers, which create a dimension of intimacy and proximity in a small space.
- The six sections converge towards a climax in the penultimate part, then dissolve in the conclusion, where only one voice remains, followed by distant bells

Music for The Terrace

Composition by Kinya Marangu

Objectives of the Composition

- Create a soundscape that celebrates the beauty of nature's nocturnal sounds
- Create a space of connection with one's inner well-being
- Create a space of openness to interactivity with the audience
- A combination of African percussion and Greek melodic instruments
- Inspiration: Oxygene Pt. 1 – Jean-Michel Jarre

Greek Instrumentation

Instruments Used:

- Aulos
- Pan Flute
- Conch Shell

Instruments Used:

- Lyre
- Arpeggiation Pad FX
- Sanctuary Pad FX

African Percussion

Instruments used:

- Shakers
- Hand Drums
- Finger Snaps

Sculptural Soundscapes

- The unique aspect to CO2 is the inclusion of Sculptural Soundscapes provided by Master Sculptor Robin Okeyo Mbera. He recorded the tools that he uses while working on a sculpture and sent them to me.
- These are meant to show the process of creating a sculpture, from getting the stone from the earth to engraving when the sculpture is complete.

Composition Process Part 1

- CO2 is a slow piece with no strict sense of tempo, with the soundscape being introduced with shakers and a low conch shell drone.
- A pan flute plays a three-note motif before a lyre plays a modal melody. That melody is then repeated in the aulos with the lyre acting as harmony.

Composition Process Part 2

- The second part of the piece is the section with Master Sculptor Robin's sculptural soundscapes. First, the listener will hear the hammer and chisel that is used when the stone is being obtained from the earth. Then a rough shape of the sculpture is created using a 9-inch Diamond Edge blade.
- Then the shapes and curves of the sculpture are revealed using a 7-inch Diamond Edge blade before final shaping with a Cap Wheel and Straight Grinder. Once the sculpture is complete, the Master Sculptor engraves his initials in the stone for provenance and authenticity with an Engraver Machine with Diamond Pin.

Composition Process Part 3

- In the final section of the piece, there is a return to Greek instruments with the three-note motif with a different starting note.
- The melody repeats one last time with the lyre and pan flute before ending with light percussion and a few more strikes of the hammer and chisel.

Sound design, Spatialization, Auralizations, Development

By Gianluca Aresu

Impulse Response recording

by Emmanouil Lianis

Balloon-pop impulses were captured in various spaces inside the Bazeus Tower using the First-Order Ambisonics (FOA) recording technique using a Zoom H3-VR recorder configured at its maximum resolution (96 kHz, 24 bit). Each balloon pop recording was repeated three to four times, allowing the cleanest waveform to be selected for the final dataset.

FIRST ORDER AMBISONICS

Ambisonics is multichannel audio technique that allows the encoding, recording, and playback of audio signals containing complete spatial information. It describes the sound field around a point as the sum of spherical modes (different reflection for each axis). It decomposes the sound into a mathematical basis (spherical harmonics) and stores and transmits the coefficients of this decomposition.

The first-order Ambisonic format consists of a W signal corresponding to an omnidirectional pickup pattern and three signals (X , Y , and Z) corresponding to figure-eight pickup patterns aligned with the Cartesian coordinate axes. In three dimensions, it is no longer sufficient to describe figure-eight patterns solely by $\sin \varphi$ or $\cos \varphi$ of the azimuth angle. It is more convenient to describe arbitrarily oriented figure-eight characteristics using the dot product between a variable direction vector (the direction of the incoming sound) and a fixed direction vector (the microphone's orientation).

So, to summarise in one sentence, ambisonics is built on spherical harmonics. W behaves like an omnidirectional capsule that measures pressure, while X , Y , and Z behave like figure-8 capsules that represent the components of particle velocity.

The Higher-orders systems use the full set of spherical harmonics.

In the mic's own coordinates, X points forward, Y to the left, and Z upward. Here we can see the orientation of the axes in the Cartesian plane (1) and visual representation of the Ambisonic B-format components as virtual microphones obtained from the spherical harmonic, we can see how they are positioned on the axes (2).

(1)

(2)

By Dr Franz Zotter
 <zotter@iem.at> - Dr
 Franz Zotter
 <zotter@iem.at>,
 CC BY-SA 3.0,
[https://commons.wiki
 media.org/w/index.p
 hp?curid=30239736](https://commons.wiki

 media.org/w/index.p

 hp?curid=30239736)

Black are with inverted polarity.

Practically, in First-Order Ambisonics (FOA) you “use four cardioid capsules in a microphone array”, oriented and spaced to capture a near 360° sound field - effectively placing the mic where your head would be, facing forward. The raw four-capsule signal is called A-Format (4 channels). It is then passed through a matrix filtering/encoding stage to produce B-Format. The output is a 4-channel WAV containing the FOA B-Format. Order higher than 1st are HOA (high order ambisonics)

Channel conventions:

- *B-Format “FuMa”:* channel order W, X, Y, Z, with W lowered by ≈3 dB relative to the others. → W (omni) - X (forward) - Y (left) - Z (up)
- *B-Format “AmbiX” (ACN/SN3D):* channel order W, Y, Z, X, with all four channels at the same nominal level. → W (omni) - Y (left) - Z (up) - X (forward)

Computing acoustical parameters of one of IR

```
Microsoft Windows [Versione 10.0.26100.4946]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. Tutti i diritti riservati.

C:\Users\Utente> cd C:\Users\Utente\Desktop\AcousticParam\AcouPar-main

C:\Users\Utente\Desktop\AcousticParam\AcouPar-main> AcouPar_pu IR0-A-1_Ambix.wav

Try opening IR0-A-1_Ambix.wav
N. of channels = 4
MaxL = 0.663488 - MaxR = 0.000000
Data written to file acoupar_pu.txt
```

Acoupar.exe - ISO3382 Acoustical Parameter File

Filename	Lsg_31.5	Lsg_63	Lsg_125	Lsg_250	Lsg_500	Lsg_1000	Lsg_2000	Lsg_4000	Lsg_8000	Lsg_16000	Lsg_A											
C50_31.5	C50_63	C50_125	C50_250	C50_500	C50_1000	C50_2000	C50_4000	C50_8000	C50_16000	C50_A	C5_Lin											
C80_31.5	C80_63	C80_125	C80_250	C80_500	C80_1000	C80_2000	C80_4000	C80_8000	C80_16000	C80_A	C80_Li											
D50_31.5	D50_63	D50_125	D50_250	D50_500	D50_1000	D50_2000	D50_4000	D50_8000	D50_16000	D50_A	D50_Lin											
EDT_31.5	EDT_63	EDT_125	EDT_250	EDT_500	EDT_1000	EDT_2000	EDT_4000	EDT_8000	EDT_16000	EDT_A	EDT_Lin											
T20_31.5	T20_63	T20_125	T20_250	T20_500	T20_1000	T20_2000	T20_4000	T20_8000	T20_16000	T20_A	T20_Lin											
T30_31.5	T30_63	T30_125	T30_250	T30_500	T30_1000	T30_2000	T30_4000	T30_8000	T30_16000	T30_A	T30_Lin											
IR0-A-1_Ambix.wav																						
88.936	97.721	100.589	98.532	101.253	99.773	99.862	90.543	70.240	98.618	106.236	113.038	22.695	24.951	23.388	14.613	8.699	7.367	9.203	10.662	13.211	21.350	24.732
36.608	19.936	28.721	31.589	29.532	32.253	30.773	30.862	21.543	1.240	29.618	29.236	34.038	-12.251	-12.006	-9.710	-9.124	-6.469	-4.165	-1.904	-0.562	1.034	-5.964
-4.343	-7.633	-10.077	-10.292	-7.694	-7.198	-3.466	-1.889	0.186	2.585	4.307	-4.202	-2.254	-5.675	5.620	5.928	9.658	10.901	18.400	27.706	39.212	46.769	55.922
20.211	26.892	14.711	516.498	563.658	498.103	417.212	303.722	208.874	137.936	89.809	86.320	269.097	230.242	334.484	6.005	6.822	6.080	5.126	4.347	3.021	2.101	1.341
1.017	3.891	3.510	4.665	7.007	6.334	5.998	4.936	4.230	3.228	2.627	1.654	2.179	4.594	4.140	5.146	7.391	5.830	5.743	5.023	4.156	3.323	2.629

ISO 3382 (series) — “Acoustics — Measurement of room acoustic parameters”

There are some acoustics parameters analysis of one of the IR’s.

RT60 (or T60): Time it takes for the sound level to decrease by 60 dB after the source stops; T20: Same idea as RT60, but the slope is measured only between -5 and -25 dB (i.e., 20 dB); EDT (Early Decay Time) = same as RT60 but only looking at the first 10 dB (0→-10 dB); C50 (Clarity 50 ms) = ratio (in dB) between the energy arriving within 50 ms and that arriving after 50 ms: > 0 dB = clear speech (early energy dominates); C80 (Clarity 80 ms) = same as C50 but the threshold is 80 ms and indicates musical definition (attacks/articulation). > 0 dB = more definition; D50 (Definition) = percentage of energy arriving within 50 ms of the total:

For speech, ~50% is good; much lower → poor intelligibility.

Convert Ambisonics format from A to B


```
1 # -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
2 import os
3 import subprocess
4 import wave
5
6 def get_audio_properties(file_path):
7     """
8     Ottiene la frequenza di campionamento e la profondità in bit del file audio.
9     """
10
11     with wave.open(file_path, "rb") as wav_file:
12         sample_rate = wav_file.getframerate()
13         bit_depth = wav_file.getsampwidth() * 8 # Converti byte in bit
14     return sample_rate, bit_depth
15
16 def extract_w_channel(input_folder):
17     """
18     Estrae il canale W dai file Ambix in una cartella e salva i nuovi file
19     rispettando la risoluzione e la frequenza di campionamento originali se superiori a 48KHz e 24bit.
20     """
21     if not os.path.isdir(input_folder):
22         print("Errore: la cartella specificata non esiste.")
23         return
24
25     # Crea una cartella di output
26     output_folder = os.path.join(input_folder, "W_channel_output")
27     os.makedirs(output_folder, exist_ok=True)
28
29     # Scansiona tutti i file .wav nella cartella
30     for filename in os.listdir(input_folder):
31         if filename.lower().endswith(".wav"):
32             input_path = os.path.join(input_folder, filename)
33             output_path = os.path.join(output_folder, filename.replace(".wav", "_wchannel.wav"))
34
35             # Ottieni le proprietà del file audio
36             sample_rate, bit_depth = get_audio_properties(input_path)
37
38             # Determina i parametri da usare
39             target_sample_rate = sample_rate if sample_rate > 48000 else 48000
40             target_bit_depth = "pcm_s32le" if bit_depth > 24 else "pcm_s24le"
41
42             # Comando Ffmpeg per estrarre il primo canale (W) e mantenere la qualità corretta
43             ffmpeg_cmd = [
44                 "ffmpeg", "-i", input_path, # File di input
45                 "-map", "0:0", # Seleziona solo il primo canale (W)
46                 "-ar", str(target_sample_rate), # Frequenza di campionamento adattata
47                 "-acodec", target_bit_depth, # Codec PCM con profondità di bit adattata
48                 output_path # File di output
49             ]
50
51             # Esegui il comando
52             subprocess.run(ffmpeg_cmd, stdout=subprocess.PIPE, stderr=subprocess.PIPE)
53             print(f"File processato: {output_path}")
54
55 # Richiede la cartella all'utente e avvia il processo
56 if __name__ == "__main__":
57     cartella_input = input("Inserisci il percorso della cartella con i file Ambix: ")
58     extract_w_channel(cartella_input)
```

Zoom Ambisonics Player software was used to convert the files from raw data (A-format, unprocessed) to FuMa or Ambix format (B-format, standardized). A customized Python script was used to extract each different channels from each recording (when/if needed)

Here we have the spectrum of all 4 Ambi FOA channel of one IR converted.

Ambisonics Encoding with IEM plugins

For each sound/track or group of tracks in the compositions, we can position the sounds in space and then, thanks to the harmonic sphere, we can obtain a complete waveform diffused in different positions. With this process, we encode the sounds into virtual sources in ambisonic format.

Source Encoder: one or more sources virtualized

Monitoring, Processing (and decoding)

You can process the ambisonics tracks before decoding (e.g MultiEQ, OmniCompressor); it is also possible to decode directly into a DAW: decoder for physical place audio reproduction for any desired loudspeaker layout or binaural decoder for headphone listening. **In our case, signal will be decoded on Wwise.**

Binaural rendering for listening with headphones

Two filters in series: we model the room (Environment Transfer Function: how the space transforms the source up to the outer ear, ETF) and the listener (Head-Related Transfer Functions, HRTFs, i.e., how head and pinnae shape the sound from outer ear to eardrum).

What HRTFs are: HRTFs are direction-dependent curves (magnitude + phase) capturing head/pinna diffraction; they are typically measured on a dummy head or with others binaural mics and then used to render what the listener would hear.

Any direction, not just measured points. If a sound comes from an in-between angle, the system computes an interpolated HRTF by weighting the nearest measured directions, so you get a valid filter for every angle.

Turning filters into sound. Dry (anechoic) audio is convolved with the room response and then with the HRTFs to produce binaural L/R signals for headphones; this yields realistic spatial cues and directivity.

Headphones & head orientation: Headphone listening needs no treated room; head orientation can be handled by expressing the sound direction in the listener's local frame (the paper analyzes this; tests used a fixed head).

We captured FOA (Ambisonic) room IRs as the environment transfer; Wwise decodes them to the ear directions and applies HRTFs to render binaural over headphones

By User:Pitbub - <http://www.sofaconventions.org/mediawiki/index.php/SimpleFreeFieldHRIR>, CC BY 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=36746864>

By PeloWisky - Own work, Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=5447646>

A sample of frequency response of ears:

- green curve: left ear $XL(f)$
- blue curve: right ear $XR(f)$

for a sound source from upward front.

THE AURALIZATION PROCESS

Historically, the technique of auralization derives from that used for over 30 years now, namely stereophonic recording using binaural microphones placed on an artificial head. This technique consisted of recording musical performances in theatres, which could then be listened to with great fidelity through headphones. At a certain point, it was realised that it was possible to separate the recording of the artistic event from its reproduction in a particular space: if music and singing are recorded in advance in an anechoic chamber, it is possible to add the effect of a particular acoustic space, in this case a theatre, by means of appropriate digital filtering of these anechoic signals. In this way, the sensation of listening in the theatre itself can be recreated with great realism, for any anechoic signal that one wishes to reproduce, without the need to re-record it in the theatre itself.

This process has been named Auralisation, in analogy to the visualisation process that allows images rather than sounds to be reproduced. Starting from the original implementation of the method, which involved the use of binaural impulse responses as numerical filters for auralisation, and which was therefore only suitable for reproduction through headphones, significant progress has been made in the last years: today it is possible to create digital filters suitable for reproducing the auralised signal on a normal pair of stereo speakers too, preferably placed at a short distance from each other (stereo dipole); furthermore, if B-Format impulse responses were measured in the theatre, it is possible to use them to achieve complete reproduction of the auralised signal according to the Ambisonics method, which involves a large number of loudspeakers placed around the listening area, with correct reproduction of three-dimensional information (including sounds coming from above or below).

At the basis of all these effects, however, there is a single, simple mathematical formula, based on the convolution between anechoic signals and numerical filters (or impulse responses, if you prefer). The mathematical theory of auralisation, in its various implementations, is presented below. The sum of N products must be calculated for each sampled data point, which produces a very high number of sums and multiplications. This calculation is performed in floating point to avoid overflow and excessive numerical noise. For these reasons, real-time “direct true convolution” can currently only be performed in cases of impulse responses a few hundred points long, while at least 100,000 points (at a sampling frequency of 44.1 kHz) are required to satisfactorily describe the impulse response of a typical concert hall. However, the convolution calculation can be significantly simplified by using FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) and IFFT (Inverse Fast Fourier Transform), since a convolution in the time domain is reduced to a simple multiplication in the frequency domain using the complex Fourier spectrum of the input signal and the impulse response.

Wwise - AK Convolution Reverb

When the Ambisonics composition is exported and imported into Wwise (as a FOA/HOA), it's routed to a dedicated Ambisonics bus and sent to an Aux hosting AK Convolution Reverb. We load a pre-recorded impulse response (IR) of the target space and convolves the incoming (dry/anechoic) signal with that IR, applying (in the frequency domain) a summation of the various sample-by-sample multiplications of the two signals on which we perform the convolution (IR and mono anechoic sounds); so the mix behaves as if it were played inside that environment. In practice, convolution sums sample-by-sample products between the IR and the source—this is the core of the auralization process.

Wwise - 6DoF - AK Convolution Reverb

6DoF = 3 translations: forward/backward, left/right, up/down (X,Y, Z); 3 rotations: (Z/vertical axis), (Y/lateral axis), (X/longit.axis)

We can send different values to the sends of the different reverb samples we have via real-time parameters (RTPC). These values change based on values sent by Unity relative to the position in the playing space. Each curve represents a different send to a specific IR of that room. So, with AK Convolution in Wwise, 6DoF is achieved by crossfading Ambisonic impulse responses tied to spatial zones, so reverb and early reflections too, how we'll see soon, update continuously with every step and head turn

Wwise - AK Reflect

Audio will be sent to AK Reflect too. For calculate early reflection in spaces. Dynamic Early Reflections (image source "driven" by geometry, type of materials, listener/emitter/walls). It is designed to generate early reflections consistent with the scene that update with movement.

AK Reflect → early reflections to instantaneous architecture;
AK Convolution → the late decay of the room (measured in IR).

Wwise - Manage audio files, decoding and routing in Wwise

Each audio is linked to an event and all together they will form a specific soundbank we have to choose the audio format and all the signal routing (the sends to the reverbs, the reflections, the main).

We have to manage the type of decoding from Ambi and manage the spread based on where we move around and all the interaction we want program

Sound position of the main sources

Here we can see 3D objects that simulate the position in space of the main movements/areas where some important sound sources are located, for example: circular movements in the Pink room or static positioning of the choir and the main voice in different points of the space in the Chapel

External Soundscape

The outdoor atmosphere adapts to each phase of the day—dawn, day, dusk, and night—with natural soundscapes composed from the sounds of Naxos and Nairobi, which change as time passes.

Unity - App Developing

The beginning starts from the architectural models, produced by Prof. Jose Manuel Revez, of each single room

Unity - Developing for VR app

In Unity, I manage the various components and materials, texture, shader, and all hierarchy and component-based behaviours (materials, texture, shaders, colliders, rigidbodies, scripts etc.), building the experience with modular scenes and reusable prefabs, additive loading, and Addressables. XR interaction uses OpenXR/XR Interaction Toolkit (input mapping, teleport/smooth locomotion, physical interactions) with triggers and lightweight state logic (Scriptable Objects/finite state). Sequences and cues are orchestrated with Timeline/Cinemachine, while rendering is optimised for Meta Quest via URP, baked lighting + light probes, occlusion culling, LOD, GPU instancing, and ASTC textures. As we have seen, audio is integrated via Wwise within Unity, but remains subordinate to the scene flow and XR interaction, so we will have assets to manage the loaded soundbanks.

C# coding for interaction in Unity and Wwise

Programming in C# offers complete freedom to create and customise any type of content and interaction designed with full control. From the creation of objects to all interactions between the user and them, including audio such as Wwise with RTPC. To name a few, including those we see in the code screenshots: rotating objects, objects that appear based on a tag, time of day controller, skyrotator, playing different sounds based on the time of day, moving to other rooms, filtering external sounds based on windows, spatialisation and auralisation, and other interactions provided in the experience.

```
DissolveOffsetControllers.cs | DayNightCycles
File esterni
1 // DissolveOffsetController.cs
2 using System;
3 using System.Collections;
4 using System.Collections.Generic;
5 using UnityEngine;
6
7 public class DissolveOffsetController : MonoBehaviour
8 {
9     [Header("Controlla dissolvenza")]
10     public bool startDissolve = false;
11     public float duration = 2f;
12     [Tooltip("Ritorno in secondo dopo la dissolvenza prima di attivare/disattivare l'oggetto")]
13     public float activationDelay = 1f;
14
15     [Header("Riferimenti esterni")]
16     public string playerObjectName = "PlayerController";
17     private CameraInteraction cameraInteractionScript;
18
19     [Tooltip("Game Object da attivare/disattivare in base alla dissolvenza")]
20     public Collider oggettoDaAttivare;
21
22     [Header("Spin Y Settings")]
23     [Tooltip("Oggetto da ruotare sull'asse Y")]
24     public Transform rotatore;
25     [Tooltip("Velocità di rotazione sull'asse Y (gradi/sec)")]
26     public float spinSpeed = 90f;
27
28     // Solo per lo spin
29     private bool canSpin = false;
30     public bool isSpinning = false;
31
32     // <summary>
33     // </summary>
34     public void SetSpinLoad(bool state)
35     {
36         canSpin = state;
37         Debug.Log($"DissolveOffsetContro
38
39     // Tutto il resto rimane com'era
40     private List<Material> materials = new
41     private float time = 0f;
42     private bool isPlaying = false;
43     private const string DISSOLVE_ROOM =
44     private float dissolveEnd = 1f;
45     private float dissolveEnd = 0f;
46     private float currentDissolveValue =
47     void Awake()
48     {
49
50     }
51     GameObject playerObj = GameObject
52     if (playerObj != null)
53         cameraInteractionScript = pla
54         ColliderActive();
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
66
67
68
69
70
71
72
73
74
75
76
77
78
79
80
81
82
83
84
85
86
87
88
89
90
91
92
93
94
95
96
97
98
99
100
101
102
103
104
105
106
107
108
109
110
111
112
113
114
115
116
117
118
119
120
121
122
123
124
125
126
127
128
129
130
131
132
133
134
135
136
137
138
139
140
141
142
143
144
145
146
147
148
149
150
151
152
153
154
155
156
157
158
159
160
161
162
163
164
165
166
167
168
169
170
171
172
173
174
175
176
177
178
179
180
181
182
183
184
185
186
187
188
189
190
191
192
193
194
195
196
197
198
199
200
201
202
203
204
205
206
207
208
209
210
211
212
213
214
215
216
217
218
219
220
221
222
223
224
225
226
227
228
229
230
231
232
233
234
235
236
237
238
239
240
241
242
243
244
245
246
247
248
249
250
251
252
253
254
255
256
257
258
259
260
261
262
263
264
265
266
267
268
269
270
271
272
273
274
275
276
277
278
279
280
281
282
283
284
285
286
287
288
289
290
291
292
293
294
295
296
297
298
299
300
301
302
303
304
305
306
307
308
309
310
311
312
313
314
315
316
317
318
319
320
321
322
323
324
325
326
327
328
329
330
331
332
333
334
335
336
337
338
339
340
341
342
343
344
345
346
347
348
349
350
351
352
353
354
355
356
357
358
359
360
361
362
363
364
365
366
367
368
369
370
371
372
373
374
375
376
377
378
379
380
381
382
383
384
385
386
387
388
389
390
391
392
393
394
395
396
397
398
399
400
401
402
403
404
405
406
407
408
409
410
411
412
413
414
415
416
417
418
419
420
421
422
423
424
425
426
427
428
429
430
431
432
433
434
435
436
437
438
439
440
441
442
443
444
445
446
447
448
449
450
451
452
453
454
455
456
457
458
459
460
461
462
463
464
465
466
467
468
469
470
471
472
473
474
475
476
477
478
479
480
481
482
483
484
485
486
487
488
489
490
491
492
493
494
495
496
497
498
499
500
501
502
503
504
505
506
507
508
509
510
511
512
513
514
515
516
517
518
519
520
521
522
523
524
525
526
527
528
529
530
531
532
533
534
535
536
537
538
539
540
541
542
543
544
545
546
547
548
549
550
551
552
553
554
555
556
557
558
559
560
561
562
563
564
565
566
567
568
569
570
571
572
573
574
575
576
577
578
579
580
581
582
583
584
585
586
587
588
589
590
591
592
593
594
595
596
597
598
599
600
601
602
603
604
605
606
607
608
609
610
611
612
613
614
615
616
617
618
619
620
621
622
623
624
625
626
627
628
629
630
631
632
633
634
635
636
637
638
639
640
641
642
643
644
645
646
647
648
649
650
651
652
653
654
655
656
657
658
659
660
661
662
663
664
665
666
667
668
669
670
671
672
673
674
675
676
677
678
679
680
681
682
683
684
685
686
687
688
689
690
691
692
693
694
695
696
697
698
699
700
701
702
703
704
705
706
707
708
709
710
711
712
713
714
715
716
717
718
719
720
721
722
723
724
725
726
727
728
729
730
731
732
733
734
735
736
737
738
739
740
741
742
743
744
745
746
747
748
749
750
751
752
753
754
755
756
757
758
759
760
761
762
763
764
765
766
767
768
769
770
771
772
773
774
775
776
777
778
779
780
781
782
783
784
785
786
787
788
789
790
791
792
793
794
795
796
797
798
799
800
801
802
803
804
805
806
807
808
809
810
811
812
813
814
815
816
817
818
819
820
821
822
823
824
825
826
827
828
829
830
831
832
833
834
835
836
837
838
839
840
841
842
843
844
845
846
847
848
849
850
851
852
853
854
855
856
857
858
859
860
861
862
863
864
865
866
867
868
869
870
871
872
873
874
875
876
877
878
879
880
881
882
883
884
885
886
887
888
889
890
891
892
893
894
895
896
897
898
899
900
901
902
903
904
905
906
907
908
909
910
911
912
913
914
915
916
917
918
919
920
921
922
923
924
925
926
927
928
929
930
931
932
933
934
935
936
937
938
939
940
941
942
943
944
945
946
947
948
949
950
951
952
953
954
955
956
957
958
959
960
961
962
963
964
965
966
967
968
969
970
971
972
973
974
975
976
977
978
979
980
981
982
983
984
985
986
987
988
989
990
991
992
993
994
995
996
997
998
999
1000
1001
1002
1003
1004
1005
1006
1007
1008
1009
1010
1011
1012
1013
1014
1015
1016
1017
1018
1019
1020
1021
1022
1023
1024
1025
1026
1027
1028
1029
1030
1031
1032
1033
1034
1035
1036
1037
1038
1039
1040
1041
1042
1043
1044
1045
1046
1047
1048
1049
1050
1051
1052
1053
1054
1055
1056
1057
1058
1059
1060
1061
1062
1063
1064
1065
1066
1067
1068
1069
1070
1071
1072
1073
1074
1075
1076
1077
1078
1079
1080
1081
1082
1083
1084
1085
1086
1087
1088
1089
1090
1091
1092
1093
1094
1095
1096
1097
1098
1099
1100
1101
1102
1103
1104
1105
1106
1107
1108
1109
1110
1111
1112
1113
1114
1115
1116
1117
1118
1119
1120
1121
1122
1123
1124
1125
1126
1127
1128
1129
1130
1131
1132
1133
1134
1135
1136
1137
1138
1139
1140
1141
1142
1143
1144
1145
1146
1147
1148
1149
1150
1151
1152
1153
1154
1155
1156
1157
1158
1159
1160
1161
1162
1163
1164
1165
1166
1167
1168
1169
1170
1171
1172
1173
1174
1175
1176
1177
1178
1179
1180
1181
1182
1183
1184
1185
1186
1187
1188
1189
1190
1191
1192
1193
1194
1195
1196
1197
1198
1199
1200
1201
1202
1203
1204
1205
1206
1207
1208
1209
1210
1211
1212
1213
1214
1215
1216
1217
1218
1219
1220
1221
1222
1223
1224
1225
1226
1227
1228
1229
1230
1231
1232
1233
1234
1235
1236
1237
1238
1239
1240
1241
1242
1243
1244
1245
1246
1247
1248
1249
1250
1251
1252
1253
1254
1255
1256
1257
1258
1259
1260
1261
1262
1263
1264
1265
1266
1267
1268
1269
1270
1271
1272
1273
1274
1275
1276
1277
1278
1279
1280
1281
1282
1283
1284
1285
1286
1287
1288
1289
1290
1291
1292
1293
1294
1295
1296
1297
1298
1299
1300
1301
1302
1303
1304
1305
1306
1307
1308
1309
1310
1311
1312
1313
1314
1315
1316
1317
1318
1319
1320
1321
1322
1323
1324
1325
1326
1327
1328
1329
1330
1331
1332
1333
1334
1335
1336
1337
1338
1339
1340
1341
1342
1343
1344
1345
1346
1347
1348
1349
1350
1351
1352
1353
1354
1355
1356
1357
1358
1359
1360
1361
1362
1363
1364
1365
1366
1367
1368
1369
1370
1371
1372
1373
1374
1375
1376
1377
1378
1379
1380
1381
1382
1383
1384
1385
1386
1387
1388
1389
1390
1391
1392
1393
1394
1395
1396
1397
1398
1399
1400
1401
1402
1403
1404
1405
1406
1407
1408
1409
1410
1411
1412
1413
1414
1415
1416
1417
1418
1419
1420
1421
1422
1423
1424
1425
1426
1427
1428
1429
1430
1431
1432
1433
1434
1435
1436
1437
1438
1439
1440
1441
1442
1443
1444
1445
1446
1447
1448
1449
1450
1451
1452
1453
1454
1455
1456
1457
1458
1459
1460
1461
1462
1463
1464
1465
1466
1467
1468
1469
1470
1471
1472
1473
1474
1475
1476
1477
1478
1479
1480
1481
1482
1483
1484
1485
1486
1487
1488
1489
1490
1491
1492
1493
1494
1495
1496
1497
1498
1499
1500
1501
1502
1503
1504
1505
1506
1507
1508
1509
1510
1511
1512
1513
1514
1515
1516
1517
1518
1519
1520
1521
1522
1523
1524
1525
1526
1527
1528
1529
1530
1531
1532
1533
1534
1535
1536
1537
1538
1539
1540
1541
1542
1543
1544
1545
1546
1547
1548
1549
1550
1551
1552
1553
1554
1555
1556
1557
1558
1559
1560
1561
1562
1563
1564
1565
1566
1567
1568
1569
1570
1571
1572
1573
1574
1575
1576
1577
1578
1579
1580
1581
1582
1583
1584
1585
1586
1587
1588
1589
1590
1591
1592
1593
1594
1595
1596
1597
1598
1599
1600
1601
1602
1603
1604
1605
1606
1607
1608
1609
1610
1611
1612
1613
1614
1615
1616
1617
1618
1619
1620
1621
1622
1623
1624
1625
1626
1627
1628
1629
1630
1631
1632
1633
1634
1635
1636
1637
1638
1639
1640
1641
1642
1643
1644
1645
1646
1647
1648
1649
1650
1651
1652
1653
1654
1655
1656
1657
1658
1659
1660
1661
1662
1663
1664
1665
1666
1667
1668
1669
1670
1671
1672
1673
1674
1675
1676
1677
1678
1679
1680
1681
1682
1683
1684
1685
1686
1687
1688
1689
1690
1691
1692
1693
1694
1695
1696
1697
1698
1699
1700
1701
1702
1703
1704
1705
1706
1707
1708
1709
1710
1711
1712
1713
1714
1715
1716
1717
1718
1719
1720
1721
1722
1723
1724
1725
1726
1727
1728
1729
1730
1731
1732
1733
1734
1735
1736
1737
1738
1739
1740
1741
1742
1743
1744
1745
1746
1747
1748
1749
1750
1751
1752
1753
1754
1755
1756
1757
1758
1759
1760
1761
1762
1763
1764
1765
1766
1767
1768
1769
1770
1771
1772
1773
1774
1775
1776
1777
1778
1779
1780
1781
1782
1783
1784
1785
1786
1787
1788
1789
1790
1791
1792
1793
1794
1795
1796
1797
1798
1799
1800
1801
1802
1803
1804
1805
1806
1807
1808
1809
1810
1811
1812
1813
1814
1815
1816
1817
1818
1819
1820
1821
1822
1823
1824
1825
1826
1827
1828
1829
1830
1831
1832
1833
1834
1835
1836
1837
1838
1839
1840
1841
1842
1843
1844
1845
1846
1847
1848
1849
1850
1851
1852
1853
1854
1855
1856
1857
1858
1859
1860
1861
1862
1863
1864
1865
1866
1867
1868
1869
1870
1871
1872
1873
1874
1875
1876
1877
1878
1879
1880
1881
1882
1883
1884
1885
1886
1887
1888
1889
1890
1891
1892
1893
1894
1895
1896
1897
1898
1899
1900
1901
1902
1903
1904
1905
1906
1907
1908
1909
1910
1911
1912
1913
1914
1915
1916
1917
1918
1919
1920
1921
1922
1923
1924
1925
1926
1927
1928
1929
1930
1931
1932
1933
1934
1935
1936
1937
1938
1939
1940
1941
1942
1943
1944
1945
1946
1947
1948
1949
1950
1951
1952
1953
1954
1955
1956
1957
1958
1959
1960
1961
1962
1963
1964
1965
1966
1967
1968
1969
1970
1971
1972
1973
1974
1975
1976
1977
1978
1979
1980
1981
1982
1983
1984
1985
1986
1987
1988
1989
1990
1991
1992
1993
1994
1995
1996
1997
1998
1999
2000
2001
2002
2003
2004
2005
2006
2007
2008
2009
2010
2011
2012
2013
2014
2015
2016
2017
2018
2019
2020
2021
2022
2023
2024
2025
2026
2027
2028
2029
2030
2031
2032
2033
2034
2035
2036
2037
2038
2039
2040
2041
2042
2043
2044
2045
2046
2047
2048
2049
2050
2051
2052
2053
2054
2055
2056
2057
2058
2059
2060
2061
2062
2063
2064
2065
2066
2067
2068
2069
2070
2071
2072
2073
2074
2075
2076
2077
2078
2079
2080
2081
2082
2083
2084
2085
2086
2087
2088
2089
2090
2091
2092
2093
2094
2095
2096
2097
2098
2099
2100
2101
2102
2103
2104
2105
2106
2107
2108
2109
2110
2111
2112
2113
2114
2115
2116
2117
2118
2119
2120
2121
2122
2123
2124
2125
2126
2127
2128
2129
2130
2131
2132
2133
2134
2135
2136
2137
2138
2139
2140
2141
2142
2143
2144
2145
2146
2147
2148
2149
2150
2151
2152
2153
2154
2155
2156
2157
2158
2159
2160
2161
2162
2163
2164
2165
2166
2167
2168
2169
2170
2171
2172
2173
2174
2175
2176
2177
2178
2179
2180
2181
2182
2183
2184
2185
2186
2187
2188
2189
2190
2191
2192
2193
2194
2195
2196
2197
2198
2199
2200
2201
2202
2203
2204
2205
2206
2207
2208
2209
2210
2211
2212
2213
2214
2215
2216
2217
2218
2219
2220
2221
2222
2223
2224
2225
2226
2227
2228
2229
2230
2231
2232
2233
2234
2235
2236
2237
2238
2239
2240
2241
2242
2243
2244
2245
2246
2247
2248
2249
2250
2251
2252
2253
2254
2255
2256
2257
2258
2259
2260
2261
2262
2263
2264
2265
2266
2267
2268
2269
2270
2271
2272
2273
2274
2275
2276
2277
2278
2279
2280
2281
2282
2283
2284
2285
2286
2287
2288
2289
2290
2291
2292
2293
2294
2295
2296
2297
2298
2299
2300
2301
2302
2303
2304
2305
2306
2307
2308
2309
2310
2311
2312
2313
2314
2315
2316
2317
2318
2319
2320
2321
2322
2323
2324
2325
2326
2327
2328
2329
2330
2331
2332
2333
2334
2335
2336
2337
2338
2339
2340
2341
2342
2343
2344
2345
2346
2347
2348
2349
2350
2351
2352
2353
2354
2355
2356
2357
2358
2359
2360
2361
2362
2363
2364
2365
2366
2367
2368
2369
2370
2371
2372
2373
2374
2375
2376
2377
2378
2379
2380
2381
2382
2383
2384
2385
2386
2387
2388
2389
2390
2391
2392
2393
2394
2395
2396
2397
2398
2399
2400
2401
2402
2403
2404
2405
2406
2407
2408
2409
2410
2411
2412
2413
2414
2415
2416
2417
2418
2419
2420
2421
2422
2423
2424
2425
2426
2427
2428
2429
2430
2431
2432
2433
2434
2435
2436
2437
2438
2439
2440
2441
2442
2443
2444
2445
2446
2447
2448
2449
2450
2451
2452
2453
2454
2455
2456
2457
2458
2459
2460
2461
2462
2463
2464
2465
2466
2467
2468
2469
2470
2471
2472
2473
2474
2475
2476
2477
2478
2479
2480
2481
2482
2483
2484
2485
2486
2487
2488
2489
2490
2491
2492
2493
2494
2495
2496
2497
2498
2499
2500
2501
2502
2503
2504
2505
2506
2507
2508
2509
2510
2511
2512
2513
2514
2515
2516
2517
2518
2519
2520
2521
2522
2523
2524
2525
2526
2527
2528
2529
2530
2531
2532
2533
2534
2535
2536
2537
2538
2539
2540
2541
2542
2543
2544
2545
2546
2547
2548
2549
2550
2551
2552
2553
2554
2555
2556
2557
2558
2559
2560
2561
2562
2563
2564
2565
2566
2567
2568
2569
2570
2571
2572
2573
2
```

Unity - App Developing

Small Room

Pink Room

Terrace

Chapel

And this is the final result of the reconstructed rooms in virtual reality

Sound Design

Lobby room

There are several sound design elements connected to interactions with objects such as: passing through the holographic sculptures in the lobby room, opening and closing the window and door, picking up the book and leafing through it. I made them using Csound and MaxMsp, edited in Ableton and encoded in Reaper for have ambisonics sources; finally routed, managed and decoded in Wwise for the virtual environment.

Bibliography

Farina, A.; Galaverna, P.; Giabbani, M. (1998). *Il processo di auralizzazione: metodologia ed esemplificazione*.

Coen, S. (2004). Intervista a Farina & Tronchin, *Convoluzione acustica e virtualizzazione dello spazio*.

Tronchin, L.; Tarabusi, V.; Farina, A.; Giusto A (2001). Spatialization and acoustical simulation in the binaural technology.

Vorlaender, Michael & Summers, Jason. (2008). Auralization: Fundamentals of Acoustics, Modelling, Simulation, Algorithms, and Acoustic Virtual Reality. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*. 123. 4028. 10.1121/1.2908264.

Zotter, Franz & Frank, Matthias. (2019). Ambisonics: A Practical 3D Audio Theory for Recording, Studio Production, Sound Reinforcement, and Virtual Reality. 10.1007/978-3-030-17207-7.

De Marco F. “Ambisonics applications in Sound Reinforcement: Looking at Room Impulse Response” *Fedele De Marco Acoustical Education*, Jan. 12, 2023; updated May 29, 2025. [Online]

Audiokinetic (2024) Wwise Fundamentals, Interactive Music, Performance Optimization, Wwise Unity Integration (Wwise 2024.1), [Online]

Unity Technologies (2025) Get started with 3D game development, XR (Unity Manual, 6000.2). San Francisco: Unity Technologies, [Online]

Institute of Electronic Music and Acoustics (IEM), IEM Plug-in Suite Documentation, University of Music and Performing Arts Graz, [Online]

Gianluca Aresu

Doctorant of the DIN programme at:
Steffani Music Conservatory in
Castelfranco Veneto
Arrigo Boito Music Conservatory in
Parma

gianluca.aresu@steffani.it

Agata Szlqzak

Doctorant of the DIN programme at:
Steffani Music Conservatory in
Castelfranco Veneto
Puccini Music Conservatory in La
Spezia

agata.szlqzak@steffani.it

Kinya Marangu

#TMMSAC Coordinator

kinya.marangu@mmskl.com

Roberto Cipollina

Student at
Conservatorio Giacomo
Puccini in La Spezia

roberto.cipollina@conssp.it

Emmanouil Lianis

Graduate of the Music
Department, National and
Kapodistrian University of
Athens. Integrated
Master's in Music
Technology

manolislianis@gmail.com

These activities are part of the CAPHE project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe strategic innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101086391. The perspectives and opinions expressed herein belong to their authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the funding institution is responsible for them.